

A method for optical testing of the HIPPARCOS instrument
and calibration of field distorsion

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Summary

It is proposed that the optical quality (MTF) of the HIPPARCOS instrument as well as the effective distorsion at the focal surface (i.e. optical distorsion plus grid distorsion) can be obtained in autocollimation, by recording the moiré pattern generated by the image of the grid superimposed on the grid itself. If the FOV is rapidly and repeatedly scanned e.g. by an IDT while the autocollimation mirror is slowly turned, there results at each point of the FOV an intensity modulation. The amplitude and phase of this modulation contain the necessary information on the MTF and distorsion, respectively. It is expected that the effective distorsion can be measured to 0".01 (0.1 μ m) or better. The optical set-up requires one flat mirror of very good optical quality, and a rather uncritical system behind the grid consisting of the illumination device, detector, beamsplitter, and some relay optics (Fig. 1).

1. The optical set-up

The proposed set-up (Fig. 1) tests the entire critical part of the instrument, i.e. the complex mirror (one surface at a time), Cassegrain system, and grid. These should be held together by the relevant parts of the actual structure: the invar tubes connecting the primary and secondary to the grid, and the honeycomb/carbon-fibre envelope connecting the complex mirror to this assembly. The relay optics and detection system of the payload are however replaced by a special unit, containing

a system for uniform illumination of the grid from the back and a two-dimensional detector (IDT) on which the focal surface is imaged. The resolution element of the detector (IFOV) should be large enough to average out the modulation by individual slits but sufficiently small that the variation of effective distortion across the resolution element is negligible (IFOV diameter about 30" would be quite suitable). The illumination system should give a wide wavelength range (white light) mimicking the actual star light and also for avoiding unwanted effects of optical interference. For the same reason the illuminating beam must have a small F-number (F/4 or less).

The autocollimation mirror should be mounted as close to the complex mirror (or rather the entrance pupil) as possible. It should have a diameter of at least 33 cm in order to accommodate the full beam from the whole FOV, and the optical quality should be very good (perhaps $\leq \lambda/50$ rms and radius of curvature ≥ 1500 km). In contrast, the stability of its mounting with respect to the instrument is not very critical. In fact, it is required that the collimation error drifts smoothly, but not necessarily in a controlled way, at a rate of a few arcsec per minute of time, which is perhaps achieved quite automatically with a moderately stable set-up. Apart from this fine motion, the autocollimation mirror must be adjustable, around two axes, within $\pm 0.5^\circ$ of the optical axis of the instrument and with a setting accuracy of about 10".

2. Principles of OTF measurement

Let $\vec{r} = (y, z)$ denote a point in the coordinate system of the grid and in particular let $\vec{m} = (y_m, z_m)$ be the autocollimation point, i.e. the point of the FOV imaged onto itself after reflection in the autocollimation mirror. In the ideal (distorsion-free) system, the point $\vec{r}$ is then imaged at $\vec{r}' = 2\vec{m} - \vec{r}$. The meaning of this is that the directions $\hat{u}$ and $\hat{u}'$ in front of the instrument corresponding to the two points $\vec{r}$ and $\vec{r}'$ are conjugate with respect to the normal $\hat{n}$ of the autocollimation mirror: $-\hat{n} = (\hat{u} + \hat{u}') / |\hat{u} + \hat{u}'|$. Now in the

real case, because of optical distortions and deviations of the grid pattern from the nominal, the directions $\hat{u}$ and $\hat{u}'$ correspond to the distorted points $\vec{r} + \vec{\Delta}(\vec{r})$ and $\vec{r}' + \vec{\Delta}(\vec{r}')$. However, the image of $\vec{r} + \vec{\Delta}(\vec{r})$ is at $2\vec{m} - \vec{r} - \vec{\Delta}(\vec{r}) = \vec{r}' - \vec{\Delta}(\vec{r}')$; hence, the relative displacement of the image with respect to the real grid is $\vec{\Delta}(\vec{r}) + \vec{\Delta}(\vec{r}')$. If the transmittance of the nominal grid is

$$g(y) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} a_n \exp(in\omega y) \quad (a_{-n} = a_n), \quad (1)$$

and if $M(\vec{r}, \vec{r}', \vec{\rho})$ is the MTF at spatial frequency $\vec{\rho}$ for a beam going twice through the instrument (from $\vec{r}$ back to $\vec{r}'$), it is found that the average transmittance of the moiré pattern at $\vec{r}$ is

$$U(\vec{r}, \vec{m}) = a_0^2 M(\vec{r}, \vec{r}', \vec{0}) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 2a_n^2 M(\vec{r}, \vec{r}', n\omega/k) \cos \left\{ n\omega \left[\Delta(\vec{r}) + \Delta(2\vec{m} - \vec{r}) - 2y_m \right] \right\} \quad (2)$$

where $\vec{r}' = 2\vec{m} - \vec{r}$, $k = 2\pi/\lambda$, and $\Delta(\vec{r})$ is the y component of the distortion $\vec{\Delta}(\vec{r})$. Note that $U(\vec{r}, \vec{m}) = U(2\vec{m} - \vec{r}, \vec{m})$.

Consequently, if y_m is varying slowly with time, the average transmittance $U(\vec{r}, \vec{m})$ is modulated according to (2) and the phase of this modulation is given by $n\omega \left[\Delta(\vec{r}) + \Delta(2\vec{m} - \vec{r}) \right]$, which may be considered as constant for several modulation periods. But since y_m is not accurately known, it is not possible to determine this absolute phase. However, the relative phase of $U(\vec{r}, \vec{m})$ at different points $\vec{r}$ of the field may well be determined if the whole field is scanned much faster than the modulation period. It is convenient to make reference to the absolute phase at $\vec{r} = \vec{m}$, viz. $n\omega \left[2\Delta(\vec{m}) - 2y_m \right]$. Knowing $n\omega$, the observable quantity is then

$$\Delta(\vec{r}) - 2\Delta(\vec{m}) + \Delta(2\vec{m} - \vec{r}), \quad (3)$$

i.e. a second-order difference of $\Delta(\vec{r})$. If (3) is obtained at a number of points $(\vec{r}, \vec{m})$, it is seen that $\Delta(\vec{r})$ can be derived apart from the terms $\Delta(\vec{r}) = c_{00} + c_{10}y + c_{01}z$, which define the origin, scale, and orientation of the grid. All higher-order terms of the distortion produce non-zero second-

order differences and can therefore be determined.

The degree of modulation at the point $\vec{r} = \vec{m}$ obviously determines $M(\vec{m}, \vec{m}, n\omega/k)$. The question is if the MTF for a single pass through the instrument can be determined from this. In theory this is quite simple: provided that the total wavefront aberration is much smaller than the wavelength, the MTF for a single pass is

$$M(\vec{m}, \vec{\rho}) = M_0(\vec{\rho}) \left\{ 1 - \frac{1}{2}k^2 \langle [\delta(\vec{x}) - (\vec{x} - \vec{\rho})]^2 \rangle \right\}, \quad (4)$$

where $M_0(\vec{\rho})$ is the ideal (diffractive) MTF, $\delta(\vec{x})$ the wavefront aberration (optical delay) from the point $\vec{m}$ in the field to a point $\vec{x}$ on a reference plane in the entrance pupil, and the average $\langle \rangle$ is over the part of the entrance pupil containing both $\vec{x}$ and $\vec{x} - \vec{\rho}$. If the beam goes back the same way through the instrument the total wavefront aberration is obviously $2\delta(\vec{x})$. It follows that

$$M(\vec{m}, \vec{\rho}) = \frac{3}{4} M_0(\vec{\rho}) + \frac{1}{4} M(\vec{m}, \vec{m}, \vec{\rho}). \quad (5)$$

Figure 1. The optical set-up for OTF measurement by autocollimation.